

The Effect of Some Amino Acids on the Corrosion of Aluminium in HCl Solution

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The use of some amino acids as corrosion inhibitors of aluminium in 2N HCl has been studied by the thermometric and weight loss methods. The two methods gave concordant results. The additives caused a decrease in the maximum reaction temperature and a corresponding reduction in the reaction number (RN). Curves representing the variation of the percentage decrease in RN with the logarithm of the molar concentration of the additives were constructed. They reveal that these additives appear to lie flat on the surface of the corroding metal. Amino acids in HCl are stronger corrosion inhibitors as revealed from the results, suggesting that adsorption occurs through both the protonated $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{NH}_3^+$ groups. The inhibition efficiency of the additives increases in the order: tyrosine > phenyl alanine > tryptophan > aspartic acid > arginine. The inhibitory character of the compounds depends upon the concentration of the inhibitor, as well as its chemical constitution.

THE corrosion of aluminium and its alloys and their inhibition by different organic inhibitors in acid solutions have been studied by several authors¹⁻⁸. The inhibitory action of some amino acids towards corrosion of aluminium in acid solutions has been investigated⁹⁻¹¹.

The methods of comparing the efficiency of inhibition are numerous¹²⁻¹⁴. Recently Aziz and Shams El-Din¹⁵ applied the Mylius thermometric method¹⁶ to study the dissolution of aluminium and zinc in hydrochloric acid solutions.

The object of this paper is to throw some light on the mode of adsorption of amino acids on the Al surface.

Experimental

Materials: B. D. H. grade tyrosine, phenyl alanine, aspartic acid, tryptophan and arginine were used without further purification. The acid (2N HCl), degreasing mixture and additive solutions were prepared as previously described¹⁷.

The impurities in aluminium sheet was as follows: Si, 0.15; Fe, 0.19; Mn, 0.005; Mg, 0.1; Cu, 0.02%. Their dimensions were 10 × 100 × 1.5 mm. The sheets were degreased and cleaned as previously described¹⁵.

Apparatus and working procedures: The reaction vessel used was basically the same as that described by Mylius¹⁶. According to this method, a test piece of the metal under study, measuring 10 × 100 × 1.5 mm, is immersed in 15 ml of 2N HCl in presence and in absence of the additives and the temperature of the system is followed as a function of time. The temperature rises, first slowly and then rapidly, to attain a maximum value and then decreases again. The reaction number RN is

defined as:

$$RN = \frac{T_m - T_i}{t} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C/min.}$$

where T_m and T_i are the maximum and initial temperatures respectively, and t is the time in minutes from the start of the experiment till the attainment of maximum temperature. The initial temperature was always $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

The procedure followed in weight loss measurements was similar to that reported previously¹⁵. The percentage inhibition of the additives was computed as:

$$100 \left(\frac{W_{free} - W_{add}}{W_{free}} \right)$$

where W is the loss in weight of the test piece.

Results and Discussion

Thermometric measurements: The dissolution of Al in 2N HCl was accompanied by temperature change. This temperature change was followed in the absence and in the presence of different concentrations of the following amino acids viz., tyrosine, phenyl alanine, tryptophan, aspartic acid and arginine.

In all cases the dissolution of Al in acid is characterized by initial slow rise in temperature followed by a sharp rise and finally decrease after attaining a maximum value. The maximum temperature (T_m) measured in the free acid is 16.2° and is attained after 20 min, while the T_m in the presence of the additives used are lower and are attained after a longer time. This indicates that additives behave as inhibitors for the dissolution of aluminium in 2N hydrochloric acid, presumably by their adsorption on the surface of the metal.

The present thermometric curves allow distinction between weak and strong adsorption¹¹. Weak adsorption is noted for all amino acids used. The curves in Fig. 1 represent this adsorption in the presence of tryptophan, in which the maximum temperature slightly decreases whilst the time necessary to reach T_m increases.

Fig. 1. Temp-time curves obtained in absence and in presence of varying concentration of tryptophan.

- (a) free acid (b) $10^{-6}M$ (c) $10^{-5}M$ (d) $10^{-4}M$
 (e) $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ (f) $10^{-3}M$ (g) $5 \times 10^{-3}M$
 (h) $10^{-2}M$ (i) $5 \times 10^{-2}M$

The fact that the compounds studied bring about a decrease in RN indicates that they act as inhibitors. The results recorded in Table 1 reveal that the efficiency of corrosion inhibition as determined from the percentage reduction in RN varies with both the concentration and the type of the amino acid used.

Concentration of the additive in M	%Reduction in RN				
	Tyrosine	Phenyl alanine	Trypto-phan	Aspartic acid	Arginine
10^{-6}	—	23.3	20.1	12.2	3.3
10^{-5}	64.4	38.1	30.1	13.2	8.3
10^{-4}	66.6	40.4	45.0	17.9	10.5
5×10^{-4}	67.7	62.3	—	28.4	16.6
10^{-3}	73.0	72.5	70.6	23.0	22.1
5×10^{-3}	79.6	78.3	71.0	41.2	31.0
10^{-2}	80.6	79.1	71.8	43.6	35.9
5×10^{-2}	92.0	85.0	80.3	46.4	39.1

The inhibition efficiency of the additives increases in the order : tyrosine > phenyl alanine > tryptophan > aspartic acid > arginine.

A plot of the percentage reduction in RN against log C is in fact similar to an adsorption isotherm (Fig. 2.). The points of inflexion in the percentage reduction in RN vs log C curves occur at $C = 10 \times 10^{-4}M$ and bear no relation to their chain length. This behaviour is explainable on the basis of a one-step adsorption process. The same conclusion can be obtained on plotting log time delay (Δt) vs log concentration (C) (Fig. 3) [time delay (Δt) is the difference between T_m in presence of the additive and T_m in absence of the additive]. These curves consist of an initial ascending portion which passes to a region of constancy indicating the completion of a monolayer of the adsorbate.

Fig. 2. % Reduction in RN-log C curves for all additives used. (a) Tyrosine (b) Phenyl alanine (c) Tryptophan (d) Aspartic acid (e) Arginine

Effect of chemical composition : It is clear that in the strong acid solution under consideration both the carboxylic and the amino groups of the additives are expected to be fully protonated. Zwitterion formation does not, therefore, contribute significantly to the actual state of the molecules in solution. Both functional groups adsorb on the cathodic sites of the corroding metal. Fig. 4 represents

Fig. 3. Log Δt -log C curves for the additives used.

the schematic presentation of the mode of adsorption of amino acids. The results indicate that the

Fig. 4

neutral amino acids (tyrosine, phenyl alanine, tryptophan) inhibit the corrosion more than the acidic amino acids (aspartic acid) and also the basic ones (arginine). Tyrosine inhibits more than phenyl alanine and tryptophan because of the presence of $-OH$ group in the p -position which increases the interaction of the delocalized π electrons with the metal surface, enlarging the coverage and enhancing the inhibitory effect at very low coverage while in tryptophan, the adsorption is via both $-NH_2$ and $-COOH$ groups, the rest of molecule being protruded in solution and free to rotate. In aspartic acid, the adsorption is through $-NH_2$ and one $-COOH$ groups while the other $-COOH$ is perpendicular to the metal surface. In arginine, the presence of unsaturation decreases the interaction of the delocalized π electrons with the metal surface and hence it gives low inhibition efficiency.

Weight loss measurements: This method was used in order to prove that the amino acids used, retard the corrosion of aluminium. The loss in the weight of aluminium strips in $2N$ HCl in the absence and in the presence of different concentrations of the additives was determined over a period of 75 min. The weight loss is plotted as a function of time for tryptophan (Fig. 5). The curves are characterized by an initial slow increase in weight loss (due to the originally formed oxide film on the surface of the metal) followed by a sharp rise (due to the breakdown of the formed oxide film on beginning of the attack). The curves obtained in presence of the additives fall below that of the free acid. It was shown that the weight loss of aluminium depends on both the type and concentration

of the additives in the same way as the percentage reduction in RN does.

Fig. 5. Weight loss-time curves for tryptophan.

(a) free acid (b) $10^{-3}M$ (c) $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ (d) $10^{-2}M$
(e) $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ (f) $10^{-4}M$ (g) $10^{-6}M$

Duplicate experiments were carried out and weight losses averaged. In Table 2 the inhibitors examined are arranged in the order of increasing inhibition efficiency. It also shows that the compounds used follow the same order when arranged according to the percentage reduction in RN at the same concentration of inhibitor ($10^{-3}M$) and after 60 min from the start.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON BETWEEN EFFICIENCY OF INHIBITORS AS DETERMINED BY THERMOMETRIC AND WEIGHT LOSS TECHNIQUES IN ACID SOLUTION

Substance	%Reduction in RN	%Inhibition
Free acid	—	—
Tyrosine	80.6	81.2
Phenyl alanine	79.1	80.1
Tryptophan	71.8	73.4
Aspartic acid	43.6	45.7
Arginine	35.9	36.7

Thus the same order of inhibitory action is obtained by weight loss and thermometric measurements. This indicates the validity of the results obtained by the two different methods for the use of amino acids as corrosion inhibitors of Al in $2N$ hydrochloric acid solution.

References

1. W. J. MULLER and E. LOW, *Aluminium*, 1936, 18, 478.
2. M. E. STRAUMANIS and Y. N. WANG, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1955, 12, 304.

3. G. DE ANGELIS and V. CARUNCHIA, *Mef. Ital.*, 1957, 49, 349.
4. F. PAVELKA, *Wien Chem. Ztg.*, 1944, 47, 52.
5. V. K. V. UNNI and T. L. RAMA CHAR, *Corros. Technol.*, 1964, 11, 35.
6. V. K. V. UNNI and T. L. RAMA CHAR, *Corros. Prev. Control*, 1965, 12, 17.
7. V. K. V. UNNI and T. L. RAMA CHAR, *Aus. Corros. Engg.*, 1965, 9, 25.
8. V. K. V. UNNI and T. L. RAMA CHAR, *Corros.*, 1966, 22, 58.
9. N. SUBRAMANYAN and K. RAMAKRISHNATH, *Proc. Semin. Electrochem.*, 1974, 14, 375.
10. I. M. ISSA, A. A. EL-SAMAHY and Y. M. TEMER, *J. Chem. U. A. R.*, 1970, 13, 121.
11. R. M. SALIH and A. M. SHAMS EL-DIN, *Corros. Sci.*, 1970, 10, 551.
12. S. KHALAF-ALLA, A. M. SHAMS EL-DIN and S. A. MEREI, *Res. Trav. Chim.*, 1959, 78, 513.
13. H. GATOS, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1954, 101, 443.
14. H. KAESCHER and N. HACKERMAN, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1958, 105, 191.
15. K. AZIZ and A. M. SHAMS EL-DIN, *Corros. Sci.*, 1966, 5, 489.
16. F. MYLIUS, *Z. Metallkde.*, 1922, 14, 233.
17. I. M. ISSA, M. N. H. MOUSSA and M. A. A. GANDOUR, *Corros. Sci.*, 1973, 13, 791.